

THE VIEWS OF TEACHERS CONCERNING THE DEGREE OF DISPLAYING TEACHER LEADERSHIP IN INFORMAL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS, AS WELL AS GOOD EXAMPLES AND APPLICATIONS OF TEACHER LEADERSHIP ENCOUNTERED

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to reveal the views of teachers concerning the degree of displaying teacher leadership in informal education institutions providing vocational training as well as good examples and applications of teacher leadership encountered. 6 master instructors from different branches and 6 master instructors from child development, who were determined by using convenience sampling, which is among purposeful sampling methods, were included in this study using qualitative research method. A semi-structured interview form and the interview technique were used in the study for the purpose of collecting data due to the fact that the study was conducted based on phenomenology design that is among qualitative research designs. In the data analysis, the content analysis technique was used. All the data acquired in the study were coded, various dimensions and convenient themes for those dimensions were determined in line with the study purpose and percentages and frequencies regarding the themes were calculated. As a result of the study, the degree of displaying teacher leadership in informal education institutions providing vocational development training, as well as encountered good examples and applications of teacher leadership were revealed.

Keywords: teacher leadership, good example, applications

1. Introduction

Leadership behaviors that are displayed by teachers who lead both formal and informal groups in the schools are among principal factors creating the school culture. It is important for a teacher, who displays leadership features in the classroom, to create a free classroom atmosphere, prepare a proper classroom climate where students can

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express themselves, and prevent factors that may destroy that climate (Can, 2009b). It can be thought that this condition is important and effective in this respect for school shareholders to feel that they belong to school, adopt school, exhibit gentle behaviors, give particular importance to conscience in their acts and exhibit charitable and collaborative behaviors.

Educational studies in which individuals from all age groups can participate and which aim to meet educational needs that cannot be met by curricula sustained in the formal education system and gain knowledge and skills for the sake of developing individuals and society are assessed within the context of informal education (Karakütük, 1990). Several master instructors are assigned to various courses in informal education institutions. Among these courses, the one with the longest duration is the child development course, which is 936 hours based on the latest regulation. Thus, the branch type with maximum assignment is master instruction in child development and child care staff, due to the long-term courses and frequency of opening the course and the fact that the most frequently applied area in vocational courses is child development. In case of heavy demand and lack or insufficiency of master instructors having a bachelor's degree in preschool teaching, it is usually possible to assign master instructors with associate degree and even high school graduate master instructors (graduated from the department of child development of a vocational school for girls or became a master instructor who are child care staff with a certificate). What attracts attention here is that child development education is the longest-termed course compared to other modules and child development master instructors are teachers working for the longest period of time in the institution because the length of course is 1032 hours in some terms and 936 hours in others. Child development master instructors who set an example and a role model for other master instructors with their experiences are considered as the backbone of informal education institutions. Occupational cooperation, Professional development and especially exhibition, workshop, training and activities are crucial for corporate advertising, promotion and generalization as well as corporate development and growth.

There are many studies in the literature concerning the need for teacher leadership in the institutions (Can, 2009a; Beycioğlu and Aslan, 2012). In this respect, there are many examples of the manner of displaying teacher leadership, as well as good examples and applications of teacher leadership in informal education institutions, which vary in terms of the type of master instruction. It is of great importance to share and display these examples and applications, convey them to other master instructors or determine the barriers and solutions. Because effective and contemporary schools should aim to raise bold individuals who have a vision and the freedom of thinking multidirectionally and internalize their own culture (Can, 2009a). According to that purpose, answers are sought to the following questions:

- 1) What are the views of master instructors from branches other than child development concerning the degree of displaying teacher leadership in informal

education institutions providing child development education, as well as good examples and applications of teacher leadership encountered?

- 2) What are the views of child development master instructors concerning the degree of displaying teacher leadership in informal education institutions providing child development education, as well as good examples and applications of teacher leadership encountered?

2. Material and Methods

This study was implemented using descriptive screening model, which tries to describe a situation or matter separately as suggested in Karasar (2009). Qualitative research technique was used in the study to conduct the abovementioned description profoundly and the study was carried out in the phenomenology design, which is among qualitative research designs (Turgut, 2009). Therefore, the interview technique and the semi-structured interview form were used in the study for the purpose of collecting data.

2.1 Sample Group

The sample group in the study was selected from the master instructors from different branches working in a school providing informal education in Konyaaltı district in Antalya city. Additionally, being one of purposeful sampling methods, convenient sampling was used. Thus, the sample consisted of 12 participants in total; 6 master instructors from child development and 6 master instructors from other branches working in an informal education institution. According to the order of interview, following codings were given to the participants: Master Instructors from different branches; M1, M2, M3, M4, M5, and M6; Master Instructors from Child Development; CDM1, CDM2, CDM3, CDM4, CDM5, and CDM6 (Kus, 2007; Mason J. 2002; Patton, 1990; Rubin and Rubin, 1995; Yıldırım and Simsek, 2006).

2.2 Personal Characteristics of the Study Group

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Master Instructors

Variable	Code	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	f
Task	Retired MI	√		√	√			3
	Normal MI		√			√	√	3
Gender	F		√			√	√	3
	M	√		√	√			3
Educational Background	Associate Degree	√	√	√	√			4
	Undergraduate					√		1
Course Type	Postgraduate						√	1
	General	√			√			2
	Occupational/ Art		√	√		√	√	4

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	0-10 years	√	√	√		√		4
Seniority	10 years and above				√		√	2
Branch	General, Art, Occupational	O	O	O	A	A	G	6

Demographic characteristics of the master instructors have revealed that there was a balanced distribution in task and gender of the instructors who participated in the interviews. Majority of them had associate degree, whereas one of them had undergraduate education and one of them postgraduate education. The master instructors were predominant in the occupational and art areas in terms of branch and nearly all of them were either young instructors having a seniority of 10 years and below or had decided to get into working life afterwards.

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of the Child Development Master Instructors

Variable	Code	CD1	CD2	CD3	CD4	CD5	CD6	f
Task	Child Care Staff	√				√	√	3
	Child Development		√	√	√			3
Gender	F		√			√	√	3
	M	√		√	√			3
Educational Background	High School	√					√	2
	Associate Degree		√	√	√			3
Branch	Undergraduate					√		1
	Child Care Staff	√		√		√		3
	Dept. of Child Development Preschool Teaching		√		√		√	3
	0-10 years							
Seniority	10 years and above	√	√	√	√	√	√	6

Demographic characteristics of the child development master instructors showed that there was a balanced distribution in variables of task type and gender. Educational background of the participants was mostly associate degree and above. There was a balanced distribution on the basis of branch. The all of the participants had a seniority of 10 years and above and they also consisted of the staffed teachers who worked in the same institution for minimum 1 year and above.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

The interview questions were prepared using the literature review and got examined by a domain expert. The questions were primarily applied by master instructor from different branches outside the individuals who participated in the study. On the basis of the feedback received from the interviews, the interview questions were put into final form. The interview questions consisted of ten questions. The semi-structured interview form included the views of the teachers from different statuses concerning good examples and applications of teacher leadership.

The purpose of the study was explained to the participants who were thought to be interviewed and then the teachers and master instructors who intended to participate in the study were determined on a voluntary basis. The researcher took notes synchronously with the interviews, lasting for approximately 30-50 minutes. The interviews were carried out in the offices and available classrooms in the course centers between September and November, 2018.

2.4 Analysis of the Data

In the study, the qualitative data of the interviews were analyzed using content analysis, which consisted of the stages of coding, finding the themes and organizing the data according to codes and themes (Balçı, 2004; Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2011). The interview records were written down by the researchers in the computer environment. Then, all the data acquired in the study were read several times and coded. Various dimensions fitting to the study purpose were detected and convenient themes were determined for those dimensions during coding. The interview texts were recoded by another researcher to provide the reliability of the analyses. In order for validity and reliability to provide the objectivity of a good qualitative research (Morse et al., 2002), a substantial consensus was achieved between the codings of the researcher and another expert and it was concluded that the process of coding was accomplished reliably.

3. Findings

This section included the findings regarding the views of the teachers from different statuses concerning the degree of displaying teacher leadership behaviors in the system of education, as well as good examples-applications/negative examples-applications of teacher leadership encountered as well as interpretations of these findings.

3.1 The Views of the Master Instructors Concerning the Degree of Displaying Teacher Leadership Behaviors in the System of Education, as Well as Good Examples-Applications/Negative Examples-Applications of Teacher Leadership Encountered

Table 3: The Views of the Master Instructors Concerning the Degree of Displaying Teacher Leadership Behaviors in the System of Education, as Well as Good Examples-Applications/Negative Examples-Applications of Teacher Leadership Encountered

Themes	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6
Leadership Attribute			√			√
Attendance, Willingness of Course Attendees		√				√
Classification						
Personal Expectations and Needs			√			
Expertise/Having Full Knowledge of the Subject				√		
Being Fair	√				√	
Ability of Mediation					√	
Competition/Discrimination					√	

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Being Disciplined	√					√
Attracting Attention	√					√

The views of the master instructors concerning the degree of displaying teacher leadership behaviors in the system of education, as well as good examples-applications/negative examples-applications of teacher leadership encountered were as follows:

“Good examples and applications should be implemented in every stage of the system of education; not only in exhibitions or celebrations. I believe that this is the only way of getting better results. I also believe that students will be more successful for teachers whom we love, respect, take as role models and in whose leadership we trust. In other words, we primarily need to accept the existence of such examples and applications instead of just ignoring them.” M1

“Good examples and applications also depend on activeness and productivity of course attendees a little. Attendance of course attendees not only gains them self-confidence, but also strengthens our leadership skill. Negative example is the lack of discipline in a course attendee. In that case, no matter what you do, you will not succeed it.” M2

“Unfortunately, there is a limited number of example behaviors that are supposed to be available in our system of education. For example, some of teachers expect presents on teacher’s day and sometimes they inflict secret punishments on their students in case of this unmet expectation. As a good example, on the other hand, some of new teachers working in courses commit themselves to the job and guide and lead their students on many issues besides education.” M3

“While some teachers have full knowledge of their subject, some do not. In such cases, the lesson becomes unfunctional and useless for attendees. As for me, the best teacher leadership is to have full knowledge of the subject, in other words to be an expert.” M4

“Such behaviors are not displayed so frequently in the system of education. The good example I had encountered is that the teacher solved a problem between two students fairly without any discrimination. She did it with mediation, which I found interesting. On the other hand, the negative example is that the students were receiving education in an extraordinary competition environment, which made some students feel insufficient and destroyed their leadership feature.” M5

“The more disciplined the course instructor is, the more disciplined the attendee group will become. On the other hand, the negative example is that the course attendees never take the instructor seriously and they are usually absent from the course and thus, fail to provide attendance. As for me, leadership is to provide their attendance. Because it will be

possible to have someone who neither gets a mark nor receives an output attend the course continuously only through making him believe in your leadership. ” M6

3.2 The Views of the Staffed Teachers Concerning the Degree of Displaying Teacher Leadership Behaviors in the System of Education, as Well as Good Examples-Applications/Negative Examples-Applications of Teacher Leadership Encountered

Table 4: The Views of the Staffed Teachers Concerning the Degree of Displaying Teacher Leadership Behaviors in the System of Education, as Well as Good Examples-Applications/Negative Examples-Applications of Teacher Leadership Encountered

Themes	CDM1	CDM2	CDM3	CDM4	CDM5	CDM6
Leadership Attribute						√
Attendance, Willingness of Course Attendees						
Making Things Difficult for Attendees	√	√		√	√	
Personal Expectations and Needs	√			√	√	
Expertise/Having Full Knowledge of the Subject	√	√		√	√	
Being Fair	√	√		√	√	
Ability of Mediation		√		√	√	
Competition/ Discrimination						√
Being Disciplined		√		√	√	
Attracting Attention	√	√		√	√	√
Talent Hunting				√	√	
Making Them Feel Special		√				√
Abundance of Bureaucracy			√			√

The views of the master instructors from child development concerning the degree of displaying teacher leadership behaviors in the system of education, as well as good examples-applications/negative examples-applications of teacher leadership encountered were as follows:

“It is too hard to tell that these behaviors are displayed in the system of education, because the system does not allow teachers to take care of students individually. Time limitations and looking for malicious intentions whenever possible are the primary factors restricting these possibilities. I would like to talk about a positive example I had witnessed. As I have mentioned above, teachers should not only take care of students’ education, but also explore their competences. The good example is completely about that. The teacher explored her student’s competences very well and advised him on the best department for him. Indeed, she also advised on the best university for that department. The student who followed that advice is now a final year student. He is perfectly pleased with his department and university and is intensely grateful for his teacher, who had helped him make a correct decision for his life. As a negative example, on the other hand, I will talk about a teacher who compelled her student instead of winning him. Every student may have a lesson that she/he is not interested şn and is not able to be taught. At

that point, the teacher should see the student in person, determine the cause of the situation, solve the problem if possible or try to minimize it. In this example, the teacher did none and failed the student. It was the Literature Lesson and although the student told his teacher that he was not interested in the lesson and thus, was going to fail, the teacher compelled him and made the situation difficult instead of comprehending it. Then the student, who couldn't help displaying impulsive behaviors, did his teacher wrong and consequently failed the lesson." CDM1

"We display teacher leadership within classroom management. If a teacher teaches sincerely and willingly, she/he displays the teacher leadership behavior more. I think that it is not known as a different form of behavior. Some teachers perform positive applications and individuals studies. They work with students and motivate them. I believe that negative behaviors include all traditional educational behaviors. The sense of mass education is a negative example. If you make students or course attendees feel special, then they will be successful and believe in your leadership sincerely." CDM2

"Such conditions cannot be observed in the system of education due to bureaucratic procedures. For example, since a teacher to lead a trip will have to check the papers of the service or face problems in a possible malfunction, she/he may sometimes not be able to fulfill that role. Thus, teacher leadership behaviors will increase in parallel with the decrease of bureaucracy." CDM3

"Leadership behavior is usually displayed for planning the future and making decisions. Just as many applications that cannot be reflected on educational environments due to deficiencies in regulations, this cannot be reflected properly, either. Because what we do is lead. Otherwise, why would a course attendee even continue? Especially long-term courses like child development bore them after a certain time; they do not even want to attend." CDM4

"There are teachers who may set a good example, just like the ones in back our childhood who had raised us. I still take them as a model. Today, on the other hand, teachers have no idea why they exactly teach. They focus on their individual goals. They have no idea about their organizational or social purposes. That being the case, there are not so many leader teachers today. I find staffed teachers inadequate in this respect. Thus, you have to develop yourself, become a leader and a pioneer example in the institution." CDM5

"Good example-application in teacher leadership primarily reminds me of a master instructor's making herself/himself accepted, liked and adopted. This is our difference from other master instructors. Indeed, as the name implies, child development is supposed to be affectionate and warm. All in all, you try to teach a profession, an approach. You will not be able to raise others unless you have self-discipline and self-respect. I take extra care of my hair, make-up and clothes. For example, I have many

rivals here. We have a competition among us. There are many staffed teachers. Additionally, majority of my colleagues are women. That's why I have to be more careful." CDM6

4. Conclusion and Discussion

When taking the results of the study into consideration in general and examining the views of the teachers concerning the degree of displaying teacher leadership in informal education institutions, as well as good examples and applications of teacher leadership encountered; it was seen that the participants mentioned many good examples and applications, however, they stated that those examples and applications could not be transferred to educational environments so much. This condition coincides with the finding in the study conducted by Beycioglu (2009) claiming that teachers are aware of the necessity and display level of teacher leadership behaviors in schools in the dimension of occupational collaboration; however, it is seen that this awareness cannot be reflected on educational environments implicitly.

It is seen that many master instructors are assigned to several courses in informal education institutions and one of the longest-duration courses is the child development course, which is 936 hours based on the latest regulation (Ministry of National Education, 2018). Thus, the branch type with maximum assignment is master instruction in child development and child care staff, due to the long-term courses and frequency of opening the course and the fact that the most frequently applied area in vocational courses is child development. In case of heavy demand and lack or insufficiency of master instructors having a bachelor's degree in preschool teaching, it is usually possible to assign master instructors with associate degree and even high school graduate master instructors (graduated from the department of child development of a vocational school for girls or became a master instructor who are child care staff with a certificate), which simply confirms the opinions stating that it is a course type displaying the example of teacher leadership behavior in informal education institutions the most.

What attracts attention here is that child development education is the longest-termed course compared to other modules and child development master instructors are teachers working for the longest period of time in the institution, because the length of course is 1032 hours in some terms and 936 hours in others. It is possible to assert that the course period and the levels of developing and reinforcing leadership behaviors are in proportion. Child development master instructors who set an example and a role model for other master instructors with their experiences are considered the wanted and essential teacher type of informal education institutions. When considering the occupational collaboration and occupational development they display and especially their exhibition and workshop studies, as well as trainings and activities they prepare; it is possible to state that corporate development and growth are of prime importance for corporate advertisement promotion and dissemination. To conclude in

this respect, we have encountered many examples of the manner of displaying teacher leadership in informal education institutions which show a variety in terms of master instruction forms, as well as good examples and applications. It could be highly useful to share and display these examples and applications, convey them to other master instructors or determine obstacles and generate solutions.

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